

Climateurope2

First assessment of organised activities and first update to the community engagement strategy

Deliverable 6.2

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About Climateurope2

Timely delivery and effective use of climate information is fundamental for a green recovery and a resilient, climate neutral Europe, in response to climate change and variability. Climate services address this through the provision of climate information for use in decision-making to manage risks and realise opportunities.

The market and needs for climate information has seen impressive progress in recent years and is expected to grow in the foreseeable future. However, the communities involved in the development and provision of climate services are often unaware of each other and lack interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary knowledge. In addition, quality assurance, relevant standards, and other forms of assurance (such as guidelines, and good practices) for climate services are lagging behind. These are needed to ensure the saliency, credibility, legitimacy, and authoritativeness of climate services, and build two-way trust between supply and demand.

Climateurope2 aims to develop future equitable and quality-assured climate services to all sectors of society by:

- Developing standardisation procedures for climate services
- Supporting an equitable European climate services community
- Enhancing the uptake of quality-assured climate services to support adaptation and mitigation to climate change and variability

The project will identify the support and standardisation needs of climate services, including criteria for certification and labelling, as well as the user-driven criteria needed to support climate action. This information will be used to propose a taxonomy of climate services, suggest community-based good practices and guidelines, and propose standards where possible. A large variety of activities to support the communities involved in European climate services will also be organised.

Executive Summary

The initial Climateurope project, which ran between 2016 and 2021, established a varied network spanning academia, NGOs, businesses, governments, and the public, totalling 388 members from 40 countries worldwide by its conclusion. These members were individually consulted about sharing their contact information for the new project and joining the Climateurope2 community. From the previous community, at the beginning of Climateurope2, 84 members joined (data provided by WP7 in November 2022).

Climateurope2 aims to expand and diversify the climate services community, in which Work Package 6 has an important task. The goal is to involve more members from southern and eastern European countries, and to involve more members outside the academic community, for example, from private organizations, governments and NGOs. Various engagement methods, including social media, Festivals, webinars, were inherited from Climateurope for community involvement. So far after 2 webinars, 2 Webstivals and one Festival, as well as appearances at several major conferences such as European Climate Change Adaptation (ECCA) conference, there are 274 (Information provided by WP7 in April 2024) members of the Climateurope2 community. Climateurope2 focuses on bolstering external initiatives to enhance community growth and engagement, evident in the substantial increase in community numbers before and after events such as the second Webstival, where membership rose from 161 to 202 participants, and the March Festival, which saw an increase to 259 members, aided by engaging content, arts, and dissemination tools.

Deliverable 6.2 “First assessment of organised activities and first update to the community engagement strategy” gives a brief overview on the activities held, and channels used and response in community engagement that they induced. It will also propose how to proceed with the activities for expanding and strengthening the climate services community.

Keywords

Climate services community, Climateurope2 network, engagement strategy, events, platform, social media, diversity, equity and inclusiveness

1 Introduction

Climate services are a fast developing field. Consultancy and government climate services aid users in managing climate risks and seizing opportunities. Despite recent development and projected growth, doubts persist about their scientific quality and user suitability. Existing quality assurance methods like [WMO guidelines](#) are limited in coverage and accessibility and urgent efforts are needed to establish minimum quality benchmarks for effective climate services. Therefore, Climateurope2 aims to support the development of accessible, effective climate services and to identify what should be the threshold of their minimum quality in an equitable manner for all sectors of society by:

- Developing standardisation procedures for climate services;
- Building a fair European network for climate services;
- Improving climate services to support adaptation to and mitigation of climate change and climate variability.

This document (D6.2) describes the first assessment of organised activities and the first update to the community engagement strategy of the Horizon Europe project Climateurope2. It describes the status of the Climateurope2 network, the overview of the implemented activities, as well as the update of the strategy to include more members of the climate services community. A publishable version of this deliverable will be available in M21 (May 2024). The strategy is a live document that is evaluated and further updated one more time during the project (D6.3). For an overview of WP6 deliverables, see Annex 1.

Climateurope2 network: everyone who is actively involved in the Climateurope2 project.

Climate services community: everyone involved with climate services as producer, user, and the ones in the intersection of the two, partly involved in the Climateurope2 network and partly not yet involved.

Neither the community nor the network are static entities. The climate services community will grow autonomously. Climateurope2 aims to enhance this growth by bringing the actors needed for standardising and for improving the quality of climate services into the community. We also aim to grow the Climateurope2 network of active participants.

This first assessment will contribute to the aims of Climateurope2, namely on strengthening the climate services community. The aim of WP6 is to promote an open exchange of knowledge, expertise and data among the climate services community to identify:

- Existing standards and remaining gaps in standardisation;
- Usable and effective labelling and certification;
- Good practices in climate services ;
- Economic, social and environmental values of using climate services;
- Current market of CS, its gaps and possible future developments;
- Decision making and policy support requirements.

WP6 is also promoting networking and exchange within the community, supporting market development and assisting other work packages in their exchanges with the climate services community.

1.1 Aims of the D6.2 First assessment of organised activities and first update to the community engagement strategy

The aims of community engagement strategy (from Grant Agreement part A):

- Establish, further develop and monitor the Climateurope2 network;
- Identify gaps in the diversity of the participants of this European climate service network
- Improve the representation of different stakeholder typologies from public and private sectors;
- Reach a greater inclusion from under-represented regions (e.g. Eastern Europe);
- Enhance the attainment of a diverse and inclusive community.
- Actively engage community members in the activities of the Climateurope2 project
- Bring the community together, enhance knowledge exchange between community members, and build links across the climate services value chain.
- Connect the Climateurope2 network to participatory processes in the project WPs, doing it in a structured and optimised way.

The strategy uses two main ways to organise interaction: communication channels and events. Communication channels are organised by WP7 and WP6 makes use of them for growing the community. Regarding the channels, three types are used for interaction:

- The Climateurope2 project website is a public medium to inform anyone interested in the aims, progress, activities and results of the Climateurope2 project and where the climate services community can share information about other relevant initiatives.
- A Climateurope2 platform will be created where the Climateurope2 network members can engage with other people working with climate services, participate in discussions about good practices, guidelines, find and share useful resources for climate change adaptation and mitigation, and access the most relevant results of the project.
- Social media channels, such as LinkedIn and Twitter are used in the project to engage with several audiences, and also the Climateurope2 network.

There are several types of events organised for interaction with the network to share knowledge, opinions, experiences and to no widen the network:

- A webinar series with stakeholders' perspectives, which are of interest for different audiences, including the private sector
- Invited webinars from other projects and initiatives
- Webstivals (online festivals) and Festivals

- A Roadshow visiting different countries across South East Europe
- Business breakfasts targeting standardisation and certification institutions and other business stakeholders.
- Sessions and side events in other conferences such as [ECCA](#), European Geosciences Union General Assembly ([EGU](#)) and European Meteorological Society meetings ([EMS](#))
- Sessions and side events in selected business arenas and conferences; the private sector needs specific engagement activities, also through intermediaries

Next to exploiting the communication channels and events, WP6 organises interaction with sister projects to widen and strengthen the network of climate services as well as the relations with interested institutions, to explore chances for further exploitation of project outcomes. WP6 extended invitations to several sister projects to participate in the agendas of two Webstivals and one Festival. Furthermore, WP6 assists with creating connections between WPs 1-5 and the climate services community. Throughout the project timeline we aim to understand their needs, for meeting standardisation requirements, and for knowledge exchange that can further equip all the work and activities of the project. Involvement of the community is critical for understanding standardisation needs and is therefore needed for providing information to key deliverables in, for example, WP1. All WPs will also have direct contacts with members of the climate services community through the mailing lists, and these interactions are expected to grow as the project progresses. WP6 offers expertise and support for new and/or better interaction. A discussion with WPs 1-5 were periodically organised to define specific aims and targets.

Throughout all the project activities WP6 is monitoring the network's diversity, equity and inclusiveness. Furthermore, other aspects are monitored, such as regional gaps (e.g. in terms of EU Member States or European countries), gender balance, age (e.g. youth engagement), and gaps in sectors or organisation types.

2 Current status of the Climateurope2 network

Since its inception in 2022 Climateurope2 has established a network of 274 climate services users and providers, spanning across sectors and countries worldwide. The efforts to broaden community representation are ongoing, with 30 members from 5 Southeast European countries. This document tracks the network's growth and introduces an updated engagement strategy aimed at enhancing member participation through activities, events and channels such as Climateurope2 platform.

The network provided a resource for knowledge sharing for climate service users and providers across Europe, and to some extent, beyond. Figure 1 shows the worldwide reach of the Climateurope2 project with network members joining from as far afield as Australia. BSC (WP7) tracks and provides all community member data, including member count, countries, sectors, and personal information. They manage the list generated from members clicking the homepage button to join the network.

Figure 1. Climateurope network density map showing the worldwide location of network members (the network list is current as of March 2024).

A growing, active climate services network is key for achieving the main objectives of the Climateurope2 project, and developing the climate service network across Europe is a main objective of WP6. From September 2022 until May 2024 the Climateurope2 community has grown rapidly. Due to active involvement of the community throughout different activities (see chapter 4) the community has 274 members spanning through different sectors and coming from different backgrounds. The most Climateurope2 community members come from Academia (98 members),

then from the Public sector (83), afterwards from the Private sector (70), while the NGO (20) and Media (2) count the lowest number of members. Initially, Climateurope2 had a higher proportion of members from academia. However, by hosting webinars tailored for the private sector (as outlined in chapter 4.2), the number of private sector members has reached 70. The project plans to conduct dedicated webinars, festivals, and activities targeting specific topics and groups. This aims to expand the community while achieving a balanced representation across sectors. Additionally, to reach the audience cross countries, the roadshow is targeted at the SEE region. To ensure gender balance throughout all activities, WP6 has developed M6.1 Guidelines for engaging with users in workshops, capacity building, and other interactions, which led to nearly equal representation of genders, achieving a balanced ratio of almost 50/50.

Climateurope2 is by definition going to amplify the community as standardisation brings new actors to the table of the climate services community. This is the case not only for standardisation organisations but also others such as organisations that provide guidance to companies in reporting climate change risk, like the TCFD¹. Also, the specific focus on standardisation of Climateurope2 should reach out to those who are not using climate services yet but for whom quality assurance and a better fit-for-purpose would make climate services attractive. WP6 will assist in further development of the network by organising events, contributing to communication channels, interacting with other WPs and with other Horizon Europe projects, as will be explained in the next chapters.

¹ Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures: <https://www.fsb-tcfd.org/>

3 Channels for engagement

This chapter explains the role of the project website, the interactive platform, and social media in engaging existing and new community members in Climateurope2. The media are owned by WP7 and WP6 will make active use of them.

3.1 Climateurope2 project website

The Climateurope2 project website, launched in October 2022 by Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC), serves as a central hub for all project-related information at <https://climateurope2.eu/>. It offers visibility and accessibility to project details and team communication. Updated in January 2024, it now includes additional sections such as "Resources" for communication materials and "Guidelines and standards." Visitor engagement metrics indicate steady traffic of total 666 visits, with Spain and Italy being the top countries, followed by Germany, the UK, France, the Netherlands and Serbia (data retrieved from WP7). The homepage highlights the project's vision, mission, latest updates, and a call to join the Climateurope2 network as seen in the figure below.

Figure 2. Homepage button to join the network

Managing the project website is a task of WP7 (Task 7.1); however, other WPs provide content for the website. The climate services community can share information about other relevant initiatives which will be shared under "Other Climate Services Events" at the event page of the website: <https://climateurope2.eu/news-events/events>. If any of the external events are of high relevance, they will also appear in the 'News and Events' section of the homepage, which lists the 3 most relevant events and news.

Present options and statistics for interaction and connectivity through the website:

- The homepage features a network join button, enabling members to participate and receive information in all project activities and receive updates. The form for joining states that Climateurope2 will use provided information to stay in touch regarding project updates. BSC

maintains the personal contact list. The homepage is updated regularly with project highlights, including events, podcasts, newsletters, deliverables, and milestones.

- The project has published three newsletters and aims for six more. Subscriptions are available on the homepage. Joining the network and subscribing to the newsletter are managed separately. Currently, 220 people are subscribed
- The website has a contact page with a form where visitors can ask questions or send comments to the project team. It also shows an email address allowing visitors to contact the project team directly (infoclimateurope2@bsc.es). These emails are received by BSC staff. WP7 monitors Google analytics, since visits to the website are one of the KPIs. Total visits to the website from April 2023 to January 2024 are 666.
- The website has a section for upcoming events, including both project-organised and external 'climate services events'. It acts as a hub for the community to find relevant gatherings.

The growing engagement across Climateurope2 channels reflects the effectiveness of the community engagement strategy since the project's inception.

3.2 Climateurope2 platform

WP7 Task 7.4 establishes the Climateurope2 platform, exclusive to Climateurope2 network members. Refer to Figure 3 for an overview of project communication vectors and the platform's position. Upon joining the Climateurope2 network, members gain access to the platform through which they can engage with peers, discuss best practices, access resources for climate change adaptation and mitigation, search for relevant documents, and visualise climate services-related information.

A beta version of the platform was delivered by MARIS in M18 available at: <https://ce2-platform-beta.maris.nl/>; this version allows for a search of project results and other relevant documents as well as community engagement. WP7 has also created a video to better explain and disseminate the beta version of the platform which was also shown at the Festival in Venice, the first on site event gathering the Climateurope2 community as well as the potential new members. (available at: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bRr_vZwlnOY).

There will be additional releases until there is a stable and final version in M36. To sustain the exploitation of the platform, an API will be developed, so it can be integrated in other platforms after the end of the project.

Figure 3. Communication vectors that are used in Climateurope2

The platform acts as a hub for work packages to engage with stakeholders, discussing best practices and gathering feedback on climate service issues. It shares project results, collects feedback, and involves the network in ongoing discussions. Its importance is emphasised across multiple work packages and will remain open for various uses (see table 1.), requiring collaboration with WPs 1-5 for full utilisation.

Table 1. Planned use of the Climateurope2 platform

Work package	Platform use planned
WP1	Inclusion of the synthesis report (the ongoing synthesis of all WPs which includes 3 milestones prior to the final deliverable in month 52).
WP2	Sharing a preliminary version of best practices and current state-of-the-art in the second stage of each task (halfway to the project).
WP3	A review of deliverable D3.3 through the platform in the third year. Discuss lessons learnt for the final deliverable D3.4.
WP4	Publish the state of the market on the platform three times (M14 (D4.2) and two updates in M28 (D4.5) and M48 (D4.10)). Share outputs of Task 4.4.

3.3 Social media

Social media are used in the project to engage with several audiences, which also includes the Climateurope2 network. The usefulness of social media platforms for interactive functions is mainly to create engagement and acquire new network members through the promotion of the project itself, its outputs, and the activities that are organised.

Climateurope developed communities on LinkedIn and Twitter. The LinkedIn account was specifically mentioned as a valuable legacy for Climateurope2. Maintenance of the LinkedIn and Twitter accounts is part of Task 7.1. Twitter and LinkedIn are mainly populated by active individuals, who can often be champions in their field and may have a large network that is not yet involved in Climateurope2.

While the social media is managed and tracked by WP7, it is useful to have an overview of the increase in number of followers and engagers, as it is another indicator of Climateurope2 community growth. Climateurope2's X account (<https://twitter.com/climateurope2>) has grown its following from 2000 to 2503, while its LinkedIn page (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/climateurope2/>) now has 648 followers compared to 399 at the end of 2023. Climateurope2 YouTube channel (see figure below) (<https://www.youtube.com/@climateurope2609>) serves as a repository for project-related recordings, including Festivals and Webstivals.

Figure 4. Climateurope2 youtube channel

3.4 Proposal for future use of channels

The cooperation between WP6 and WP7 has been very fruitful. Together with other work packages, WP6 produces a lot of content for the website. The subscription link helps to grow the community

and to do this within GDPR guidelines. The Climateurope2 platform is still under development and WP6 events can be used to promote it and invite users. Social media are also used, but we think we can make more use of the extended network of each person within the Climateurope2 consortium to reach out more, for example, through LinkedIn.

4 Events for engagement

4.1 Climateurope2 webinars

To date, 3 webinars have been conducted: one by the University of Leeds and BSC focusing on UK climate services standards and value, the second jointly organised by Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change (CMCC) and Center for the Promotion of Science (CPN) addressing the Art and science towards climate action, while the third addressed Uncertainty communication on climate services, organised by Centre Européen de Recherche et de Formation Avancée en Calcul Scientifique (CERFACS). Mentioned webinars have been recorded and uploaded to the project website in compliance with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) regulations.

At least 6 webinars will be organised in total, starting from year 2. The webinars will be stakeholder targeted including salient topics and narratives which will be of interest for different audiences, including the private sector - all in aim to foster community engagement and its continuous growth.

4.2 Webstivals and Festivals

Under Climateurope2, WP6 and CMCC organised two Webstivals in M6 and M12, four more Webstivals are planned to be organised throughout the project timeline (M24, M31, M45, M52).

The Climateurope2 virtual Festival, first Webstival, convened policymakers, entrepreneurs, researchers, and climate experts to address current challenges in climate services. Through various engagement styles, it aimed to raise awareness and foster dialogue. Featuring 500+ participants and 65+ speakers, topics spanned renewable energy, sustainable food systems, climate-smart cities, and EU Mission regions. Relevant EU-funded projects like Adaptation-oriented Seamless Predictions of European ClimaTe (ASPECT) and CLIMAtE risk and vulnerability Assessment framework and toolbox (CLIMAAX) also shared insights.

The second Climateurope2 webstival centred on the themes of businesses and communities, highlighting Europe's transformation via climate services and tailored solutions and had 230 participants. The two-day Webstival featured diverse engagement formats like high-level panels and thematic dialogues, aimed at raising awareness and fostering dialogue for wider climate service adoption.

The first Climateurope2 in-person event was the Festival organised in March (11-13th) in Venice. The three day event with the title "Bridging science, services and standards for a climate-resilient future," incorporated diverse topics, speakers and tools for community engagement. It included a combination of plenary sessions and interactive formats such as World Cafés. In addition, a marketplace allowed visitors to network and learn about other projects and initiatives. With over 100 participants present on-site, the Festival incorporated four overarching themes - urban and water management and challenges, EU mission on climate change, and Communicating climate knowledge - Bridging the gap. The event was filmed, and all the material is available on Climateurope2 Youtube channel. The WP6 and WP7 team has also performed and filmed 24

interviews with participants (both external and consortium members) which represent the video capsules. Festival participants came from various sectors including Research & Academia, NGOs & Associations, Public Administration, Business, Media.

After every event WP6 has sent out a feedback survey to all the participants. For outcomes of implemented activities and events, please see chapter 4.3. The following chapter does not only include feedback gathered from the survey but also from the consortium members that were present on events.

4.3 Proposal for future use of Webstivals, Festivals, and other events

As both Webstivals and the Festival were successful and engaging based on the overall satisfaction of 4.28 (based on the feedback survey responses) and amount of events' participants (over 100), WP6 proposes the following tools and recommendations which were useful to incorporate into planning further activities throughout the project timeline. The recommendations also include feedback survey responses from event participants, and suggestions from consortium partners (collected on WP6 meetings):

- Adapt to the audience and community:
 - Search for relevant topics and themes.
 - Consider the optimal length of Webstivals; shorter durations may be more appealing.
 - Ensure timely dissemination of Webstival information to promote the event and foster community participation.
- Feedback mechanisms:
 - Send out feedback surveys promptly after the event to capture responses while they're fresh.
 - Collect feedback from the participants during the events also.
- Program Committee:
 - Form a program committee responsible for curating event programs.
 - Maintain an active team to continuously organise and improve event logistics.
 - Schedule timely meetings to coordinate event planning efforts.
- Community engagement:
 - Listen to the needs of the community and adapt event offerings accordingly.
 - Utilise art as a powerful tool to enhance community engagement and promote climate services.
 - Increase networking opportunities:
 - Host structured networking workshops.
 - Allocate time and space for community networking during events.
- Unique event features:
 - Incorporate innovative elements like the [Climate Capsule](#) into event marketplaces to generate interest and engagement.

- Including art and science exhibitions and elements to it can engage the audience on a bigger level (bigger interest, more participants, and it is adapted to general public and diverse audience).
- Distinguish from conventional conferences:
 - Ensure events provide consistently engaging content tailored to the interests of the Climateurope2 community.
- Supporting material:
 - Besides the strategy, WP6 has delivered a milestone - *Guideline for engaging with users in workshops, capacity building and other interactions available* that contains useful information on organising events, and how to include gender dimension, carbon neutrality and some useful tools for creating surveys, interviews and evaluations. Additionally, since this is a long document, WP6 created a checklist to efficiently cover all the important points to keep in mind when planning a project activity and/or event.

4.4 Roadshow

A roadshow is a series of smaller events happening in different countries across South East Europe (SEE). It is planned in the second half of the project. Its aim is to promote the Climateurope2 network in the region of SEE, through local stakeholder engagement in their native languages.

The roadshow is set to tour 10 locations in SEE from M10 to M48. It kicks off in five cities: Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina; Skopje, North Macedonia; Rijeka, Croatia; Tirana, Albania; and Kotor, Montenegro.

CPN is organising this travelling climate action, featuring various engaging activities and exhibitions related to climate services. One highlight is "M1L3NA," an interactive climate storytelling installation, the winning project of the Climateurope2 art and science open call in 2023. Besides M1L3NA, CPN will use various artistic pieces and exhibitions alongside the Climate capsule.

To continue engaging the community, CPN will launch a second call for artistic projects for future roadshows and the 2025 Belgrade Festival. As seen throughout the Venice Festival, Art has proven to be an effective tool for engaging the public, including climate change professionals, and remains integral to our community engagement strategy.

In addition to exhibitions, CPN will host climate services conferences in each location, facilitating dialogue among users and providers on local issues. This fosters knowledge exchange and community expansion on a regional level.

4.5 Sessions and side events in other conferences

European conferences covering topics like climate change and climate adaptation are interesting venues for engaging new audiences. Some relevant scientific conferences are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Conferences with relevance for the Climateurope2 network

Acronym	Full title	Schedule	Audience
ECCA	European Conference on Climate Change Adaptation	Every 2 years, 2023	Scientific and non-scientific climate adaptation community
EGU	European Geosciences Union	Yearly in April (Vienna)	Scientists in the Earth, planetary and space sciences
EMS	European Meteorological Society	Yearly in September (2023 in Bratislava)	Meteorological, climatological and related communities
ICRC-CORDEX	International Conference on Regional Climate - Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment	25-29 of September 2023 in Trieste, Italy	Researchers worldwide in climate data downscaling efforts
ESOF	EuroScience Open Forum	Every 2 years	Diverse audience - Scientists, Policy makers, Students, General public, etc.

Here are the outcomes of the conferences visited by Climateurope2 consortium:

In June 2023, Climateurope2 researchers showcased the project at the **ECCA** Conference in Dublin, featuring expert video testimonials and promoting the upcoming Climateurope2 Webstival. We also held a session on climate service standardisation and another session on engagement strategies, drawing significant participation.

In September 2023, the **CORDEX** Conference in Trieste gathered experts to discuss high-resolution regional climate models and Climateurope2 members co-convened a session on climate services methods and future development.

In October 2023, **Adaptation Futures**, the leading global conference on climate change adaptation, was held in Canada, where a Climateurope2 poster was showcased.

EGU24, The European Geosciences Union Assembly, which took place in Vienna in April 2024 hosted over 20000 people from various scientific backgrounds. The European Geosciences Union is the leading organisation for Earth, planetary and space science research in Europe. Climateurope2 partners from CMCC and CPN were organisers of poster and oral sessions on Telling climate stories: platforms, tools, and methodologies for accurate and engaging science communication.

These events have demonstrated their value in fostering community engagement, disseminating project updates, and showcasing results. WP6 intends to maintain its presence at these events in the future to sustain engagement and interaction. Furthermore, the list of possible events might extend.

5 Interaction with other projects

Some projects are explicitly mentioned in the grant agreement because several work packages need to be built on them (see Table 3).

Besides this, the consortium populated a longer list of relevant sister projects and initiatives, whose members can be invited to join the network (Table 4). Initial sister projects, funded for the Climate Adaptation Mission, were identified at project start, while later ones, were found through interactions, contacted to explore partnerships, exchange information, and increase visibility through website publication.

Continuously fostering external initiatives remains a core strategy for Climateurope2, aimed at strengthening community growth and enhancing engagement. A clear indicator of success lies in the comparison of community numbers before and after events, showcasing significant expansion. For instance, prior to the second Webstival, the Climateurope2 community comprised 161 participants, which has grown to 202 members post-event. Similarly, the Festival in March saw an increase to 259 members. This approach, coupled with the utilisation of effective tools like engaging content, arts, and dissemination, positively contributes to the community's growth.

Table 3. Relevant projects from the Grant Agreement

Work package	Projects, programs and organisations	Audiences
WP1	Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures (TCFD)	Financial sector
	Standardisation organisations	Business community
WP2	IPCC AR6 and Data Distribution Center (DDC)	Researchers in climate change, adaptation and mitigation, policy makers and stakeholders
	ESA CCI - European Space Agency - Climate Change Initiative	Climate data producers
	IS-ENES3 - Infrastructure for the European Network for Earth System Modelling	Climate modellers, climate data producers and climate data users
	RDA - Research Data Alliance	Owners of climate data

WP4	MARCO - Market Research for a Climate services Observatory	Climate service providers
	EU-MACS - European Market for Climate Services	Climate service providers and users
	European Research Programs including the EU Mission on Climate Adaptation and Societal Transformation	Wide range of researchers and research users
	Climate-KIC	Climate service providers
	Copernicus C3S	Climate service providers
	JPI Climate	Climate, adaptation and mitigation researchers
	WMO - World Meteorological Organisation	Meteorologists, climate scientists
	GFDRR - Global Facility for Disaster Reduction and Recovery (World Bank)	Climate service users
WP5	ERA4CS	Climate data users, adaptation and mitigation researchers
WP6	CSP - Climate Services Partnership	Climate service providers
	GFCS - Global Framework for Climate Services (WMO)	Governments and organisations that produce and use climate information and services
WP8	EOSC- European Open Science Cloud	Climate data producers and data users
	HORIZON-CL3-2022-DRS-01-03 Horizon Topic Improved quality assurance / quality control of data used in decision-making related to risk management of natural hazards, accidents and CBRN events	Climate service providers
	HORIZON-CL4-2022-RESILIENCE-01-21 Horizon Topic Leveraging standardisation in Digital Technologies (CSA)	Standardisation community

	HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-18 Horizon Topic Fostering standardisation to boost European industry's competitiveness (CSA)	Standardisation community
	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D2-01-13 Horizon Topic Strengthening Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) research communities in climate, energy and mobility disciplines	Climate service users
	HORIZON-MISS-2021-CLIMA-01-01 Horizon Topic Better prepared regional and local authorities to adapt to climate change	Climate service users
	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-03 Horizon Topic Maximising the impact and synergy of European climate change research and innovation	Climate service providers and users

Table 4. Sister projects

Acronym	Full name and description	URL	Project coordination	Funding	End date
MAGICA	Maximising the synergy of European research governance and innovation for climate action	[no project website, but use this:] https://jpi-climate.eu/programme/magica/	Basque Centre for Climate Change (BC3). Project coordinator: María José Sanz mj.sanz@bc3research.org	Horizon 2020	5/31/26
MAIA	Maximising impact and accessibility of European climate research	[no website yet, use]	Fondazione Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici (CMCC) Project coordinator: Dr Giulia Galluccio,	Horizon 2020	8/31/25

			giulia.galluccio@cmcc.it		
I-CHANGE	Individual change of habits needed for green European transition	https://ichange-project.eu/	Centro Internazionale in Monitoraggio Ambientale - Fondazione CIMA info@ichange-project.eu	Horizon 2020	4/30/25
HARMONIA	Support system for improved resilience and sustainable urban areas	http://harmonia-project.eu/	Politecnico di Milano Project coordinator: Julia Tzortzi julia.georgi@polimi.it	Horizon 2020	1/31/25
SOCIO-BEE	Wearables and drones for city socio-environmental observations and behavioural change	https://socio-bee.eu/	Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis Project coordinator: Evangelos V. Kopsachellis ekops@iti.gr	Horizon 2020	30/11/2024
COMPAIR	Compair Community Observation Measurement & Participation in AIR Science	https://www.wecompair.eu/	Digital Vlaanderen (Digital Flanders) (BE) digitaal.vlaanderen@vlaanderen.be	Horizon 2020	31/10/2024
EIFFEL	Earth Observation applications for climate change adaptation and mitigation	https://www.eiffel4climate.eu/	Institute of Communication and computer Systems	Horizon 2020	5/31/24

PROTECT	Procuring innovative climate change services	not available yet, we could add the cordis link https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060592]	Marc Pattinson mpattinson@group-gac.com	Horizon 2020	5/1/24
ECFAS	European coastal flood awareness system	https://www.ecfas.eu/	Istituto Universitario di Studi Superiori di Pavia (IUSS), Italy Project coordinator: Ruth Higgins (Dr.) ecfas.project@gmail.com	Horizon 2020	31/12/2022
E-SHAPE	A cloud-based contribution to Earth Observation	https://e-shape.eu/	Francesca Piatto francesca.piatto@earsc.org	Horizon 2020	30/04/2023
FIRE	Forum for Innovation and Research in European Earth Observation	https://fire-forum.eu/	Natassa Antoniou natassa.antoniou@earsc.org	Horizon 2020	30/11/2022
Climateurope	European climate observations, modelling and services	https://www.climateurope.eu/	MET OFFICE	Horizon 2020	31/01/2021
IMPETUS 4 CHANGE	Improving near-term climate predictions for social transformation	https://impetus4change.eu/	i4c-pmo@norceresearch.no	Horizon Europe	
CLIMAAX	CLIMAtE risk and vulnerability Assessment framework and toolbox	https://www.climaax.eu/	Deltares. Project coordinator: Frederiek Sperna, Frederiek.SpernaWeiland@deltares.nl	Horizon RIA	31/12/2026

REACHOUT	Shaping climate resilient cities	https://reachout-cities.eu/	Deltares. Project coordinator: Joletta.deMan@deltares.nl	Horizon 2020	31/03/2025
IMPETUS	Turning climate commitments into action	https://climate-impetus.eu/	Eurecat	Horizon 2020	30/09/2025
VALORADA	Validated Local Risk Actionable Data for Adaptation	https://valorada-project.eu/	Dr. Cristobal Reveco Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon GmbH	europe	312026

During the first Webstival the following initiatives were included as speakers in the agenda During the first Webstival we cooperated with ASPECT, CLIMAAX, REACHOUT, PROTECT, E-SHAPE, VitiGEOSS. During the second Webstival CLIMAAX , PIISA and VALORADA were a part of the event and presented their work.

The following initiatives and project were a part of the Venice Festivals' agenda:

- AGORA
- ARCADIA
- AREA EUROPA
- ASPECT
- CLIMACQUILA
- COALESCE
- DAKU BLUE GREEN ROOF
- DESIRMED
- DestinE
- ESABCC
- GEMWET
- GWP-MED
- I-CHANGE
- MEDECC
- METEO TRACKER - IOTOPON
- MIP4Adapt
- PATH2RESILIENCE
- PEERS
- PIISA; NATURANCE
- PROVIDE
- REACHOUT, DESTINATION EARTH
- SAFERPLACES
- TALANOA

- TRANSCEND
- UDENE
- Waterjade

6 Involvement of WPs in community engagement

Involving the climate services community is a shared effort that requires coordination within the Climateurope2 project. The community is critical for understanding standardisation needs and is therefore needed for providing information to key deliverables in, for example, WP1. Community members should experience coherence in the approach and activities. To achieve this, internal communication is needed about the stakeholder engagement every WP plans to do.

Climateurope2 consists of 33 partners. To ensure ongoing communication and engagement across WPs, WP6 has devised a cross-WP strategy. WP6 members regularly attend meetings of other WPs to stay informed of their initiatives and activities, providing brief WP6 [presentations](#) during these gatherings. In addition to board meetings and WP1 to WP5 meetings, WP6 seeks to solicit feedback from other WPs, fostering cross-communication and facilitating connectivity amongst the consortium's size. Alongside presentations, WP6 has developed a community building roadmap encompassing both internal and external efforts (Figure 5). The internal roadmap emphasises coherent work and collaboration amongst WPs towards driving active community engagement. The external roadmap attracts new members and ensures that existing ones stay informed and engaged.

Figure 5. Community building roadmap: internal and external strategy

As shown in the figure above, the Climateurope2 consortium will invite more members to our community. While externally, the consortium will send existing material such as infosheets and/or newsletters, and go to their external events rather than only inviting potential community members to attend our events. The main strategy to attract new members is to always show what potential community members get once they become a part of our network:

- Stakeholder engagement and **networking** (Climateurope2 hosts diverse activities and

- events, providing excellent opportunities to connect with the wide range of stakeholders)
- **P2P** (During these events, we extend invitations to various projects, allowing potential members to establish valuable connections in a project-to-project format)
 - Be a part of a **great climate initiative** (Climateurope2 represents a project of over 30 partners which jointly work towards equitable and quality-assured CS for society)
 - Exclusive Access to climate services Information: Members gain firsthand insights into climate services and standardisation, with interactive opportunities facilitated through the **Climateurope2 platform**.
 - Joining the projects community provides access to both our events and exclusive opportunities at external gatherings, giving members a VIP experience

7 Methods to monitor progress of the network

The aim of the project is to expand the network beyond what was achieved in Climateurope, both in quantitative terms and in diversity. In order to achieve these goals, we monitor the progress to find out in what areas extra efforts are needed. In addition, we try to find out what methods and measures work, and if we need to try different alternatives for achieving diversity across the network as well as equity and inclusion regarding the participation of network members in the project activities. Diversity can refer to personal characteristics such as age and gender, but also to geographic diversity across Europe and diversity in types of stakeholders (e.g. public and private, different economic sectors). In this update of the Climateurope2 engagement strategy, each method described will be considered and assessed according to its effectiveness.

The total number of community members is a Key Performance Indicator for WP6 (See Table 5 for the KPIs of WP6). The number of individuals participating in the network are monitored. Next to this we acquire data on the size of the organisations they are part of; assuming that the knowledge they acquire will impact their organisations and thus increase the impact of the Climateurope2 project.

Table 5. WP6 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

KPI #	KPI description	KPI target
6.1	Number of stakeholders in the managed community	>300 in total
6.2	Attendees at the events organised to support the community (Festivals, Webstivals, roadshow)	>500
6.3	Overall satisfaction with the event assessed through evaluation form	More than 3.5 on average
6.4	Attendees at user perspectives webinar series	>300
6.5	Attendees to business breakfasts	>50

A monitoring tool will be developed for tracking the network's diversity. Aspects to be monitored are regional gaps (e.g. in terms of EU Member States or European countries), gender balance, age (e.g. youth engagement), and gaps in sectors or organisation types. We will set benchmarks rather than targets, and we can go with the data-driven quota approach, e.g. the gender balance can be 40/60 in a community where there are realistically 40% of those who identify as female, and 60% of those who identify as male, in order to acquire a more realistic sample of the community. Another way to go would be the inclusion strategy, e.g. we can set the benchmark for involving certain regions, wherein we want to oversample e.g. Eastern Europe, since this region was less involved in Climateurope. The diversity guideline provides input for the monitoring.

Methods we can use to track progress are analysis of contact form interactions via the project website, feedback from stakeholders at events, surveys and interviews. Post-event surveys are planned after each of the events organised by Climateurope2. Progress will be reported in the updated versions of the Engagement Strategy (M21 and M33). Monitoring diversity may involve sensitive personal data, which should be collected, managed and stored considering the GDPR guidelines.

Annex: Task 6.1 in Grant Agreement

Task 6.1 Establish, monitor and develop the European climate service network [M1-M50] (CPN lead, REH, WR, CMCC, Ecologic, RHMZ, SMHI, BSC, MetOffice)

Building on Climateurope's legacy and other activities (e.g. JPI-Climate/ERA4CS, C3S, CSP, GFCS, and the European Climate Pact), this task will **establish and monitor the Climateurope2 network**. The task will also **identify gaps in the diversity of the participants** of this European climate service network and develop a **strategy to improve the representation of different stakeholder typologies** from public and private sectors, reach a **greater inclusion from under-represented regions** (e.g. Eastern Europe) and **enhance the attainment of gender balance** across the network. A **concise live document describing the network status and including a Community Engagement Strategy will be available in M9 (D6.1)** and updated twice in the project lifetime to monitor the network evolution and engagement and adjust the strategy to reach low-represented and highly-relevant communities. This will include analysis of potential biases in the established community (e.g. gender and other biases). The data collected in WP6 will be analysed to understand the network dynamics and relevant results will be published for the benefit of the wider community including recommendations for the legacy and sustainability of the network beyond the project lifetime (D6.5).

Figure 6. Work package 6 deliverable legend

Table 6. WP6 Deliverables

Deliverable #	Deliverable title	Due month
D6.1	Community Engagement Strategy	M9 (delivered)
D6.2	First assessment of organised activities and first update to the community engagement strategy	M21
D6.3	Intermediate assessment of organised activities and second update to the community engagement strategy	M33
D6.4	Final assessment of organised activities and recommendations for future events	M46
D6.5	Recommendations for the future sustainability and improvement of the network and community, and the development of new forums based on lessons learnt	M50